

TEACHERS' DIGITAL LITERACY AND PEDAGOGICAL INTEGRATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING: BASIS FOR A TRAINING PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the relationship between teachers' digital literacy and pedagogical integration of Information Communication and Technology in teaching that could lead to an outcome of a training enhancement program in the North Bondoc Peninsula, Quezon Province. Based on the findings, the level of teachers' pedagogical integration of ICT was generally high. The level of pedagogical integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of Lesson Planning, Preparation of Instructional Materials, Delivery of Instruction, and Assessment of Learning were all often integrated by the teachers. There is a significant relationship between digital literacy and information and communication technology in lesson planning and online-based conferences and assessment of learning to productivity of software tools. The problems met in information and communication technology in teaching were claimed to be sometimes encountered. The coping mechanisms of teachers to address challenges in pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in their teaching were claimed to be sometimes. A training program is designed for the enhancement of ICT Pedagogical Integration in teaching.

Keywords: *Digital Literacy, Integration, Information Communication and Technology and Teaching*

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technology in education allows for new education for both teachers and students. Online or e-learning is increasingly growing in popularity with various unprecedented events taking place in our lives. It not only chances for schools to ensure that learners have access to instructional resources in the classroom, but it also enables them to ensure pupils in settings other than the classroom, like homes.

Information may be received in numerous formats, including text, video, sound, and images, so in considering that there is technology available that generates these kinds of data and when any of these are combined, it refers to technology that is mobile. For instance, cellphones, digital cameras, and video cameras. The need to enhance the digital literacy of teachers, especially in the Province of Quezon, North Bondoc Peninsula, may be considered as the top priority of DepEd as many technological advancements are already available such as training and seminars for ICT Pedagogical Integration are already in place for the betterment of digital literacy.

When ICT is integrated into lessons, teachers and learners become more engaged in their work. It is because technology provides different opportunities to make it more fun to teach the same things in many ways. In this increased engagement, learners retain knowledge more effectively and efficiently. One of the skills for the 21st century includes evaluating, planning, monitoring, and reflecting. Effective use of ICT in education requires the ability to justify and explain how ICT is used to solve problems. Students must debate, take tests, and think about the different strategies they might employ. Education aims to prepare a labor force that will meet the demands of the society.

In education, information and communication technology has received enough attention. ICT has been integrated into the development plans of the United Nations and other international education partners. Teachers must be prepared with new pedagogical competencies and new approaches to teacher education in order to effectively use technology in the classroom. Instructors ought to learn about the objectives of policy and be able to recognize the different facets of education reform that are connected to these goals.

In the Schools Division of Quezon, Evardome et al. (2019) stated that most of the teachers in DepEd Quezon have basic competence in demonstrating continual growth in technology knowledge and stay abreast of current and emerging technologies who can select and use the correct terminology to describe functions of current and emerging hardware, software, and network-related resources used for classroom settings. Either old or new have insufficient time whenever they prepare technology-based lessons. It could be attributed to a lack of technological and pedagogical content knowledge in technology-integrated lessons. Lack of proper equipment may also be the reason since only a few teachers have personal laptops.

As DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012 Grades 1 to 10 of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and DepEd Order No. 021 s. 2019 Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which mandate and core objectives include incorporating a

comprehensive and strategic digital literacy plan in Philippine education match with the K-12 curriculum. Further, this research study would establish a better outlook on ICT Pedagogical integration as digital literacy is already a need. ICT will continue to be a significant part of our future as it connects to more and more parts of our lives. It will continually evolve and change because consumers like a choice.

The Theory of Connectivism by Siemens G. (2005) acknowledged that technology is a major factor in the educational process and that being always linked offers possibilities for selecting the source of the teachers who will do its role. Also, it promotes participation in group activities and conversation, allowing for a variety of viewpoints and points of view when it comes to making decisions, resolving issues, and comprehending information. Connectivism encourages learning that takes place external to an individual,, specifically through social media, online networks, blogs, or information databases. It relies heavily on technology, introducing more opportunities for digital learning to the learners.

The theory of Task Technology Fit by Goodhue D. & Thompson R. (1995) discussed a holistic understanding of how the user, particularly the teacher, chooses the information technology that affects its performance, assesses usage impacts, and matches the task to the technology characteristics. The appropriateness of task technology and task characteristics can be affected, which determines user performance and usage, behavioral intention to use, and actual media use, specifically in practicing the integration of ICT during teaching and learning. It relates that if the technology fits the user's tasks and workflow, the user will use technology during these tasks and vice versa. If the technology interrupts the user's workflow and tasks, the user will not use it or try to avoid it.

It discussed how the user and the teacher choose the information technology that affects performance, evaluates usage effects, and matches the task to the technological characteristics. The appropriateness of task technology and task characteristics can be affected, which determines user performance and usage, behavioral intention to use, and actual media use, specifically in practicing the integration of ICT during teaching and learning.

In assumption, the teacher must be technologically informed to improve digital literacy abilities of learners. They are expected to provide students with relevant and current experiences that will enable them to engage effectively with digital technology and prepare them for 21st-century skilled life after school. As a result, to meet the current demands of 21st-century learners and have an enhanced teaching-learning process, teachers must be digitally upgraded.

Every digitally literate teacher helps to provide the learner with the abilities and technically innovative skills needed to achieve K-12 standards. In connection with this, the researcher however observed that the lack of study on the level of digital literacy of teachers and the level of integration of information and communication technology (ICT) and its relation, particularly in the Province of Quezon, North Bondoc Peninsula, despite the increasing technological innovations and rapid advancement in education as thru

integrating information and communication technology in teaching barrier have seen challenging in the teacher's role in education. The researcher is prompted to conduct this study on the Teachers' Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching: Basis for a Training Program.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between Teachers' Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching that could lead to an outcome of a Training Program in the North Bondoc Peninsula.

Specifically, this study looks for the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' digital literacy in terms of:
 - 1.1 Productivity Software Tools,
 - 1.2 Website Browsing,
 - 1.3 Social Media Platforms,
 - 1.4 Learning Resource Management System,
 - 1.5. Online-Based Conference Platforms?
 2. What is the level of pedagogical integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of:
 - 2.1 Lesson Planning,
 - 2.2 Preparation of Instructional Materials,
 - 2.3 Delivery of Instruction,
 - 2.4 Assessment of Learning?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between digital literacy and pedagogical integration of information and communication technology integration in teaching?
 4. What are the problems met by the teachers in pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in teaching?
 5. What are the coping mechanisms of the teachers to address the problems met in the pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in their teaching tasks?
 6. What training program could be proposed for the enhancement of pedagogical integration of ICT in teaching?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted at the North Bondoc Peninsula, located in the Quezon Province, Philippines, encompassing 102 schools, 82 elementary and 20 secondary schools. These schools are distributed in six districts, Padre Burgos, Agdangan, Unisan,

Pitogo, Macalelon, and General Luna, situated in the Quezon Province. The researcher selected the North Bondoc Peninsula as the research locale to benefit more from the output in this paper. This study was inclusive of those districts as they are all in the Quezon Province.

Teachers in public schools were the study's target population in the North Bondoc Peninsula. Information and communication technology is taught to learners, so teachers are more interactive and innovative in their teaching approach. The result of their teaching was correlated with the school heads as respondents. The study used simple random sampling conducted in the North Bondoc Peninsula.

Since the entire population represents the data set with an equal probability of being chosen, the respondents chose samples through the wheel of names or the random name picker. It would provide a fair representation of a group. Deperso G. (2024) stated that simple random sampling culls a smaller size from a larger population and uses it to research and generalize the group. All respondents answered the self-made questionnaire and ensured its confidentiality.

Table 1

Respondents of the Study

North Bondoc Peninsula Municipalities	No. of School Heads		No. of Teachers	
	Population	Sample Size	Population	Sample Size
Padre Burgos	17	14	203	49
Agdangan	8	7	116	28
Unisan	19	15	226	54
Pitogo	19	15	219	53
Macalelon	20	17	228	55
General Luna	19	15	219	53
Total	102	83	1211	292

Table 1 shows the Population and Sample of the respondents. The researcher used Slovin's Formula to determine the sample size derived from the population. Ellen S. (2020) stated that it allows for the sampling of the population by a researcher with a desired degree of accuracy and provides guidance on the required sample size to guarantee a respectable level of result accuracy.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a self-made survey questionnaire to gather data from the respondents consisting of two Parts.

Part I of the research instrument consists of the item that gathers the data for a statement of the problem number 1 level of teachers' digital literacy in Productivity Software Tools, Website Browsing, Social Media Platforms, Learning Resource Management Systems, and Online-Based Conference Platforms. Statement of problem number 4 was the problems met in information and communication technology in teaching. Statement of problem number 5 was the coping mechanisms of the teachers integrating information and communication technology in their teaching tasks.

This questionnaire contained the Likert scale to measure the level of teachers' digital literacy challenges met in information and communication technology in teaching and coping mechanisms of the teachers integrating information and communication technology in their teaching tasks. The respondents of Instrument number 1 are the teachers through the following descriptive scale:

Table 2
Descriptive Scale for Digital Literacy

Point Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	Very High (VH)	The teacher has a very high level of literacy ranging from 76% to 100%.
4	High (H)	The teacher has a high extent of literacy ranging from 51% to 75%.
3	Moderately (M)	The teacher has a moderate extent of literacy ranging 26% to 50%.
2	Low (L)	The teacher has a low extent of literacy ranging 1% to 25%.
1	None (N)	The teacher has no literacy.

This study used a descriptive scale for the teachers' digital literacy. A point scale of 5 is interpreted as Very High with the qualitative description of teacher has a very high extent of literacy ranging from 76% to 100%, scale of 4 is interpreted as High with the qualitative description of teacher has a high extent of literacy ranging from 51% to 75%, point scale of 3 are interpreted as Moderately with the qualitative description of teacher has a moderate extent of teacher has a literacy ranging 26% to 50%, teacher has a low extent of literacy ranging 1% to 25%, and point scale of 1 are interpreted as None with the qualitative description of teacher has no literacy to 0%.

Table 3
Descriptive Scale for Problems Met

Point Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	Always (A)	The teacher frequently encountered problems to an extent equivalent to 5 to 7 days a week.
4	Often (O)	The teacher frequently encountered problems to an extent equivalent to 4 days a week.
3	Sometimes (S)	The teacher frequently encountered problems to an extent equivalent to 3 days a week.
2	Rarely (R)	The teacher frequently encountered problems to an extent equivalent 1 to 2 days a week.
1	Never (N)	The teacher does not encounter problems at all.

This study used a descriptive scale for the Problems Met. A point scale of 5 is interpreted as Always Encountered with the description of a teacher is frequently encountered problems to always extent equivalent to 5 to 7 days in a week, scale of 4 is interpreted as Often Encountered with the description of teacher is frequently encountered problems to often extent equivalent to 4 days in a week, point scale of 3 are interpreted as Sometimes Encountered with the description of the teacher is frequently encountered problems to sometimes extent equivalent to 3 days in a week, point scale of 2 are interpreted as Rarely Encountered with the description of the teacher is frequently encountered problems to sometimes extent equivalent 1 to 2 days in a week, and point scale of 1 are interpreted as Never Encountered with the description of The teacher do not encountered problems at all.

Table 4
Descriptive Scale for Coping Mechanism

Point Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	Always (A)	The teacher frequently copes with the problems using the mechanism 20 or more times a month.
4	Often (O)	The teacher frequently copes with the problems using the mechanism 15 to 19 times a month.
3	Sometimes (S)	The teacher frequently copes with the problems using the mechanism 10 to 14 times a month.

2	Rarely (R)	The teacher frequently copes with the problems using the mechanism 5 to 10 times a month.
1	Never (N)	The teacher does not use the copes mechanism.

Descriptive scale for coping mechanisms of the teachers to address the problems met in the pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in their teaching tasks. The point scale of 5 is interpreted as Always with the qualitative description of teachers frequently copes with the problems using the mechanism 20 or more times a month. Point scale of 4 is interpreted as often meant copes the problems using the mechanism 15 to 19 times a month. Point scale of 3 is interpreted as sometimes copes with the problems using the mechanism 10 to 14 times in a month. Point scale of 2 is interpreted as rarely coping with the problems using the mechanism 5 to 9 times a month, and point scale of 1 is interpreted as Never, which meant teachers do not use the coping mechanism.

Part II of the research instrument consists of the items that gathers the level of integration of information and communication technology in teaching in terms of Lesson Planning, Preparation of Instructional Materials, Delivery of Instruction, and Assessment of Learning.

This questionnaire used the Likert scale to measure the level of teachers' digital literacy, problems met by the teachers in the integration of information and communication technology in teaching, and coping mechanisms of the teachers to address the problems met in the pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in their teaching tasks. The respondents of Instrument number 2 were the School Heads through the following descriptive scale:

Table 5
Descriptive Scale for Level of Integration of ICT

Point Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	Always (A)	The teacher frequently integrates ICT to constant extent equivalent to 5 to 7 days in a week.
4	Often (O)	The teacher frequently integrates ICT to often extent equivalent to 4 days in a week.
3	Sometimes (S)	The teacher frequently integrates ICT to sometimes extent equivalent to 3 days in a week.
2	Rarely (R)	The teacher frequently integrates ICT to rarely extent equivalent 1 to 2 days in a week.
1	Never (N)	The teacher do not integrate ICT at all.

The descriptive scale for information and communication technology in teaching in Lesson Planning, Preparation of Instructional Materials, Delivery of Instruction, and Assessment of Learning:

The point scale of 5 is interpreted as Always with the qualitative description of frequently integrates ICT to a constant extent equivalent to 5 to 7 days in a week, point scale of 4 is interpreted as Often with the qualitative description of frequently integrates ICT to often extent equivalent to 4 days in a week, point scale of 3 is interpreted as sometimes with the description of frequently integrates ICT to sometimes extent equivalent to 3 days in a week, point scale of 2 is interpreted as rarely with the qualitative description of frequently integrate ICT to rarely extent equivalent to 1 to 2 days in a week, and point scale of 1 is interpreted as never with the qualitative description of frequently integrates ICT to never extent equivalent to do not integrate ICT at all.

- In terms of validation purposes, the researcher identified three experts from different fields and professions to test the validity of the research instrument. For Research Instrument 1, the validators were composed of experts, mainly an ICT coordinator, a School Principal, and a Master Teacher. For Research Instrument 2, the validators were composed of a School Principal and a Master Teacher.

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the researcher asked permission to conduct study through sending letter to the Office of Schools Division Superintendent, after the approval, the researcher communicated with Public Schools District Supervisors in the North Bondoc Peninsula of Third Congressional District of Province of Quezon for their consent to conduct surveys and administer the questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher used a self-made survey questionnaire as an instrument to collect the data with a 5-point Likert Scale. For Part 1, the respondents are teachers and master teachers, and the data collected are the level of digital literacy in terms of productivity software tools, website browsing, social media platforms, learning resource management system, and online-based conference platforms, frequently of problems met by the teachers and coping mechanisms of the teachers. For Part 2, the respondents are the school heads, and the data collected are the Level of ICT Pedagogical Integration in terms of Lesson Planning, Preparation of Instructional Materials, Delivery of Instruction, and Assessment of Learning.

Upon approval of the request, the researcher gave a written orientation to the respondents in the 6 districts, with the supervision of the Public Schools District Supervisors, Google Form and Survey Form was disseminated and used to collect the data. After retrieving the raw data, the researcher tabulated using spreadsheet. Afterwards, it was forwarded to statistician to analyzed and interpreted.

The result of this study is a Training Program designed based on the analysis of the results. The output entitled Training Program for Enhancement of ICT Integration will be provided to the Master Teachers and Teachers.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. Data were tallied and encoded into a master list of the data collection sheet using Microsoft Excel.

The researcher used means to describe the level of teachers' digital literacy in terms of Productivity Software Tools, Website Browsing, Social Media Platforms, Learning Resource Management Systems, and Online-Based Conference Platforms, Likewise, level of integration of information and communication technology in teaching in terms of Lesson Planning, Preparation of Instructional materials, Delivery of Instruction, Assessment of Learning was used to describe the mean. Meanwhile, Spearman Rho was used to determine the relationship between the level of teachers' digital literacy and pedagogical integration of ICT, the mean scores were interpreted using the scale in Table 6.

For Statement of Problems 4 and 5, mean scores were used to determine problems met by the teachers in the integration of information and communication technology in teaching and coping mechanisms of the teachers to address the problems met in the pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in their teaching tasks it was verbally interpreted using the 5-point Likert scale.

RESULTS

Part 1. Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy

Table 7

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of using Word Processing Tools.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can type using capitals and lowercase text.	4.87	Very High
can delete both ways using the backspace and delete keys	4.80	Very High
can use undo and redo	4.84	Very High
can change font type, size of the font & color of the font and know when to use these	4.90	Very High
can align text left, right, center, and justify and know when these are used	4.85	Very High
can move a word or section of text within the document by cutting and pasting	4.80	Very High
can check spelling and grammar	4.78	Very High
can orient the page view and page size and print on different sizes of paper	4.82	Very High
can insert a picture, word art or clipart	4.86	Very High

can save a copy of the document as a pdf file	4.76	Very High
General Mean	4.83	Very High

Legend: "Very High (4.51 - 5.00)", "High (3.51 - 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)", "Low (1.51 - 2.50)", "None (1.00 -1.50)"

Table 8

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can identify a cell reference	4.39	High
can enter, edit, or delete data into a cell	4.61	Very High
can select a cell or a range of cells	4.46	High
can modify column width and row height	4.57	Very High
can format data: font, size, color, and style	4.55	Very High
can merge and center data	4.62	Very High
can apply number formats to data	4.43	High
can alter the number of decimal places	4.38	High
can calculate the total number using the auto-sum	4.28	High
can cut, copy and paste a selection of cells	4.54	Very High
General Mean	4.48	High

Legend: "Very High (4.51 - 5.00)", "High (3.51 - 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)", "Low (1.51 - 2.50)", "None (1.00 -1.50)"

Table 9

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of using Presentation Tools.

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can open and create a presentation	4.73	Very High
can insert and format slides	4.75	Very High
can configure a presentation for print	4.70	Very High
can insert and format shapes and text boxes	4.68	Very High
can insert and format images	4.74	Very High
can insert and format tables	4.71	Very High
can insert and format charts	4.59	Very High
can apply slide transitions	4.68	Very High
can set the timing for transitions and animations	4.58	Very High
can finalize presentations	4.62	Very High

General Mean	4.68	Very High
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Legend: “Very High (4.51 - 5.00)”, “High (3.51 - 4.50)”, “Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)”, “Low (1.51 - 2.50)”, “None (1.00 -1.50)”

Table 10
Respondents’ Ratings on the Level of Teachers’ Digital Literacy in terms of Website Browsing

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can access the internet	4.78	Very High
can use navigational buttons: back, home, go, refresh, history	4.64	Very High
can enter URL by typing or pasting	4.65	Very High
can perform basic internet search	4.76	Very High
can know email address and password	4.66	Very High
can compose, send, open, read, reply to, and forward messages	4.66	Very High
can store and retrieve email messages	4.58	Very High
can add, use, and manage bookmarks/favorites	4.40	High
can access and use blogs, wikis, discussion boards, and similar interactive sites	4.29	High
can download and save files from the internet including image, audio and video	4.58	Very High
General Mean	4.60	Very High

Legend: “Very High (4.51 - 5.00)”, “High (3.51 - 4.50)”, “Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)”, “Low (1.51 - 2.50)”, “None (1.00 -1.50)”

Table 11

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of Social Media Platforms

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can use social media to communicate information to students.	4.55	Very High
can use social media to do research work.	4.42	High
can use social media for content delivery in teaching.	4.54	Very High
can use social media for online academic group discussions.	4.34	High
can use social networking sites to seek information.	4.39	High
can use social media as a platform for engaging with your learners for educational purposes.	4.36	High
can integrates the use of social media in lessons if needed.	4.46	High
can encourage interaction with students through social media platforms.	4.31	High
can encourage collaboration among students through social media platforms.	4.36	High
can use social media to share learning resource materials among students.	4.43	High
General Mean	4.42	High

Legend: "Very High (4.51 - 5.00)", "High (3.51 - 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)", "Low (1.51 - 2.50)", "None (1.00 -1.50)"

Table 12

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of Learning Resource Management System

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can use DepEd learning resource system.	4.26	High
can access DepEd learning resource portal.	4.16	High
can navigate interface features in learning resource website.	3.97	High
can upload and organize learning resources into website.	3.98	High

can create illustrations and other materials useful for developing a localized material using learning resource.	4.07	High
can download materials teaching resource in the portal.	4.29	High
can publish teaching materials that are appropriate for the learners.	3.93	High
can create teaching materials and learning resource using embedded tools.	3.93	High
can integrates the use of learning resource management system in lesson if needed.	4.10	High
can search appropriate materials to provide the learner's needs.	4.26	High
General Mean	4.09	High

Legend: "Very High (4.51 - 5.00)", "High (3.51 - 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 - 3.50)", "Low (1.51 - 2.50)", "None (1.00 - 1.50)"

Table 13

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of Online-Based Conference Platforms

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
can utilize different online-based conference platforms	4.02	High
can easily navigate the different online-based conference platforms	4.03	High
can use many applications and as an instructional aid during video conferencing	3.98	High
can schedule and launch video lectures	3.86	High
can share files and slide shows, exchange messages in chat, or share their screens with students.	4.07	High
can host webinars that significantly help in attracting more students to engage	3.78	High
can guide learners in need using online-based conference platforms.	3.93	High
can choose appropriate online-based conference platforms that will use to deliver instruction.	3.84	High
can online-based conference platforms in assessing the learners.	3.81	High
can provide feedback to learners using online-based conference platforms.	3.93	High
General Mean	3.93	High

Legend: "Very High (4.51 – 5.00)", "High (3.51 – 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 – 3.50)", "Low (1.51 – 2.50)", "None (1.00 – 1.50)"

Part 2. Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology

Table 14

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of Lesson Planning

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
integrates the word processing in lesson planning	4.16	Often
integrates desktop publishers in lesson planning	3.75	Often
integrates web search engines for references	3.95	Often
integrates download resources from the internet	4.25	Often
integrates ICT in drills in lesson planning	4.24	Often
integrates ICT in the review of the lesson in lesson planning	4.11	Often
integrates ICT in motivation in lesson planning	4.06	Often
integrates ICT in a presentation in lesson planning	4.11	Often
integrates ICT in application in lesson planning	4.05	Often
integrates ICT in evaluation in lesson planning	4.00	Often
General Mean	4.07	Often

Legend: "Very High (4.51 – 5.00)", "High (3.51 – 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 – 3.50)", "Low (1.51 – 2.50)", "None (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 15

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of Preparation of Instructional Materials

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teachers...		
integrates Word processors (Word etc.)	4.12	Often
integrates Spreadsheets (Excel etc.)	3.93	Often
integrates Presentation Software (PowerPoint, Canva etc.)	3.95	Often
integrates Databases (Access etc.)	3.71	Often
integrates Web Browsers (Google etc.)	4.14	Often
integrates Search Engines (Chrome, Firefox etc.)	3.99	Often
integrates Electronic Mail (e-mail)	4.00	Often
integrates Learning Resource Management System (LMDS)/ Learning Portals	3.87	Often
integrates video editing software (e.g. Adobe Premiere Pro, Kinemaster, Capcut etc.)	3.86	Often
integrates graphics editing software (e.g. Adobe Illustrator, Photoshop)	3.72	Often
General Mean	3.93	Often

Legend: "Very High (4.51 – 5.00)", "High (3.51 – 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 – 3.50)", "Low (1.51 – 2.50)", "None (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 16

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of Delivery of Instruction

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
integrates presentation tools for the delivery of lesson (Powerpoint etc.)	4.23	Often
integrates live stream videos/images in presentation of lesson	4.02	Often
integrates downloaded videos/images in presentation of lesson	4.04	Often
integrates E-books/articles in presentation of lesson	3.53	Often
integrates online video conferencing in lesson	3.40	Sometimes
integrates online group discussion for his/her lesson	3.53	Often
integrates offline interactive games during class session	3.82	Often
integrates online interactive games during class session	3.82	Often
integrates audio-based instruction during the delivery of lesson	3.88	Often
integrates infographic during the delivery of lesson	3.66	Often
General Mean	3.79	Often

Legend: "Very High (4.51 – 5.00)", "High (3.51 – 4.50)", "Moderate (2.51 – 3.50)", "Low (1.51 – 2.50)", "None (1.00 – 1.50)"

Table 17

Respondents' Ratings on the Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology in terms of Assessment of Learning

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
integrates Word Processing tool in assessment (Microsoft Word etc.)	3.95	Often
integrates Presentation tool in assessment (Powerpoint etc.)	3.87	Often
integrates Spreadsheet tool in assessment (Google sheet, excel, etc.)	3.90	Often
integrates Online based quiz game in assessment (Kahoot, Quizzer, Mentimeter, etc.)	3.54	Often
integrates google classroom in assessment	3.42	Sometimes
integrates online survey forms in assessment (Google Forms, Microsoft Forms)	3.58	Often
integrates cloud drive (e.g. Google Drive, Dropbox) for submission of outputs	3.69	Often
integrates interactive Name picker (The Hat, Duck Race, Wheels of Names etc.)	3.43	Sometimes

integrates Automated QR Code to evaluate the learners performance	3.41	Sometimes
integrates data derived from the result assessment integrated by ICT Tools	3.64	Often
General Mean	3.64	Often

Legend: “Very High (4.51 – 5.00)”, “High (3.51 – 4.50)”, “Moderate (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Low (1.51 – 2.50)”, “None (1.00 – 1.50)”

Part 3. Test for Significant Relationship Between Digital Literacy and Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching

Table 18

Spearman Rank Significant Relationship Between Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of ICT in Teaching in terms of Lesson Planning

Lesson Planning					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Productivity Software Tools	-0.144	Weak Negative Correlation	0.195	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Website Browsing	-0.188	Weak Negative Correlation	0.090	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Social Media Platforms	0.075	Weak Positive Correlation	0.502	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Resource Management System	0.009	Weak Positive Correlation	0.936	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Online-Based Conference Platforms	-0.279	Weak Negative Correlation	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: “If the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject Ho; otherwise, fail to reject Ho.”

Table 19

Spearman Rank Significant Relationship Between Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of ICT in Teaching in terms of Preparation of Instructional Materials

Preparation of Instructional Materials					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Productivity Software Tools	0.141	Weak Positive Correlation	0.202	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Website Browsing	0.095	Weak Positive Correlation	0.394	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Social Media Platforms	0.126	Weak Positive Correlation	0.256	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Resource Management System	0.161	Weak Positive Correlation	0.147	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Online-Based Conference Platforms	-0.179	Weak Negative Correlation	0.106	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject Ho; otherwise, fail to reject Ho."

Table 20

Spearman Rank Significant Relationship Between Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of ICT in Teaching in terms of Delivery of Instruction

Delivery of Instruction					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Productivity Software Tools	0.068	Weak Positive Correlation	0.540	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Website Browsing	-0.062	Weak Negative Correlation	0.580	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Social Media Platforms	0.096	Weak Positive Correlation	0.389	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Resource Management System	0.073	Weak Positive Correlation	0.512	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Online-Based Conference Platforms	-0.109	Weak Negative Correlation	0.325	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
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Note: "If p -value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 21

Spearman Rank Significant Relationship Between Digital Literacy and Pedagogical Integration of ICT in Teaching in terms of Assessment of Learning

Assessment of Learning					
Indicators	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Productivity Software Tools	0.251	Weak Positive Correlation	0.022	Reject Ho	Significant
Website Browsing	0.072	Weak Positive Correlation	0.519	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Socia Media Platforms	0.074	Weak Positive Correlation	0.507	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Learning Resource Management System	0.193	Weak Positive Correlation	0.080	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Online-Based Conference Platforms	-0.066	Weak Negative Correlation	0.553	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Note: "If the p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject Ho; otherwise, fail to reject Ho."

Part 4. Problems Met in the Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching

Table 22

Respondents' Ratings on the Problems Met in the Integration of Information and Communication Technology in Teaching

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher...		
lacks expertise in integrating ICTs	2.91	Sometimes
lacks technical support	2.96	Sometimes
lacks genuine/licensed ICT Software tools	3.17	Sometimes

lacks a stable internet connection	3.22	Sometimes
lacks internet connection	3.25	Sometimes
lacks time to integrate ICT into classroom teaching	3.10	Sometimes
lacks confidence in using ICT in classroom teaching	2.84	Sometimes
lacks training in using ICT in classroom teaching	2.98	Sometimes
lacks interest in using ICT in the classroom	2.70	Sometimes
lacks availability of access to computer hardware	2.83	Sometimes
General Mean	2.99	Sometimes

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)”, “Rarely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Sometimes Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)”, “Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)”

Part 5. Coping Mechanisms of the Teachers’ Integration of Information and Communication Technology in their Teaching Task

Table 23

Respondents’ Ratings on the Coping Mechanisms of the Teacher’s Integrating Information and Communication Technology in their Teaching Task

Indicators	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Teacher.... lacks expertise in integrating ICTs.	Teacher.... learns independently	3.71	Often
lacks technical support	seeks technical support to software used in teaching	3.42	Sometimes
lacks genuine/ licensed ICT Software tools.	purchase genuine/licensed ICT Software tools.	3.19	Sometimes
lacks a stable internet connection	seeks technical support from internet providers	3.36	Sometimes
lacks internet connection	seeks administration support from internet connectivity	3.16	Sometimes
lacks time to integrate ICT into classroom teaching	seeks allotted time for preparation for integrating ICT in classroom teaching	3.37	Sometimes
lacks confidence in using ICT in classroom teaching.	seeks motivation to peers in using ICT in the classroom teaching	3.49	Sometimes
lacks training of using ICT in the classroom teaching.	seeks training of using ICT in the classroom teaching.	3.54	Often

lacks interest using ICT in the classroom.	seeks goals in using ICT in the classroom.	3.62	Often
lacks access to computer hardware	requests administration support for computer hardware	3.54	Often
General Mean		3.44	Sometimes

Legend: “Never (1.00 – 1.50)”, “Rarely (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Sometimes (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Often (3.51 – 4.50)”, “Always (4.51 – 5.00)”

DISCUSSION

Table 7 presents the teacher’s ratings on their Level of Digital Literacy regarding Productivity Software Tools, specifically in word processing. Generally, teachers claim that their literacy in word processing tools is very high, with a general mean of 4.83. In all the indicators, they reported that they are very highly literate. This implies that teachers always use word processing tools in their daily tasks in school, although sometimes, they encounter challenges.

Additionally, they have been trained in using these tools since college, and DepEd also provides related training. Another reason is the continued integrating and training given by the school and ICT coordinators to ensure teachers can cope with the 21st-century teacher’s need for digitalization.

In terms of mastery in using Microsoft Word, the study by Bayucca (2020) they were revealed that teachers displayed a proficient extent of knowledge in basic computer commands and word processors. However, some of the skills enumerated in each group have a low mean and were close to the adjacent group scale of the lower level of knowledge, such as Google Apps and other advanced computer applications, which are also necessary for the constructing of instructional materials. While the teachers' self-assessment showed they are proficient in the basic skills enumerated under Microsoft Word, there is still a further need for training.

Table 8 reveals the data showing teachers’ ratings on the Level of Teachers’ Digital Literacy regarding Spreadsheet tools. They claimed that they are highly proficient in this kind of productivity tool.

Analyzing the results, teachers’ literacy ranges from high to very high. This affected the frequency of their use of the spread tools, which is only during the preparation of grades.

It can noted that the lowest rating calculated with a mean rating of 4.28. It may show that teachers have difficulties using formulas in the spreadsheet. These results agree with the findings of the study by Obenita et al. (2019) that teachers MS Excel adopt

different commands, especially when computing or consolidating the grades of students. The teachers described it as accurate with less time and effort.

The teachers were also perceived as effective and helpful in their use of spreadsheets; however, there are still factors to be considered to increase their efficacy, especially in terms of their expertise with the Excel program. There are still some points that they need plausible assistance to strengthen their expertise on the use of the program. Table 9 presents the surveyed responses of teachers about the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in terms of the Presentation tool. As teachers claimed, they have very high literacy in all indicators, with a general mean of 4.68.

This may conclude that teachers are competent in creating and presenting using presentation tools due to their frequent use of the teaching task. It is noted that teachers constantly undergo different training and LAC sessions relating to the utilization of tools.

Along with the teachers' skills in creating presentation tools, teachers integrate highly into creating different presentation tools. It was aligned with the study of Boonmoh et al. (2022), which also revealed that teachers feel free and easy to use to create learning content. Further, most of the teachers knew of technological tools and had integrated technologies into their classes. Meanwhile, certain types of tools were already used by all the teachers while Networked educational technology tools were only being integrated in some classrooms. It may be concluded that why the teachers, creating presentation tools, mainly were very highly literate.

Table 10 presents the Teacher's Ratings on the Level of Teachers Digital Literacy in terms of Website Browsing. The survey claimed that browsing websites demonstrate a very high level of literacy, with a general weighted mean of 4.60.

It is due to their frequent use of websites in their daily work, creating, preparing, and utilizing different strategies and techniques in teaching involving browsing websites.

Moreover, teachers who are highly literate in accessing and using blogs, wikis, discussion boards, and similar interactive sites and adding, using, and managing bookmarks and favorites have less frequent use than the other indicators.

Parallel to the result of the study of Kurebay et al. (2023), they revealed in the study that primary school teachers essentially utilize the Internet for information access, academic information sharing (homework, projects, and others.), and professional and personal development. Academic, research, and educational sites, web browsers (Google, Yandex, etc.), dictionary sites, social networking sites (Facebook, MySpace, Friendfeed, Google Plus, etc.), "wikis," and "video and photo sharing sites" were among the resources that Kazakh teachers utilized most frequently. Another study finding indicated that while primary school teachers' perceptions of their efficacy in using the Internet were at a medium level, their perceptions of their teaching efficacy were at a high level.

Table 11 reveals the level of teachers' digital literacy in terms of social media platforms. The above presents the tabulated data illustrating generally Highly Literate as claimed by the teachers with a 4.42 mean.

Teachers have social media applications on their mobile phones and laptops. It is also a part of their daily activity to connect and communicate through social media. Aguilar et al. (2021) study supported the study's result of how teachers nowadays use social media platforms in teaching. They revealed in their study that teachers' social media was personal, despite the uptake of social media platforms and their purposes. Additionally, teachers' use of social media changed noticeably after the pandemic began; multilevel models showed that teachers were more likely to connect and share on social media.

Table 12 presents data that revealed teachers' responses on the Level of Teachers' Digital Literacy in the Learning Resource Management System. They claimed that they are highly literate, based on the results of the general weighted mean score of 4.09.

In conclusion, it demonstrates that teachers are digitally literate based on learning resource management. Teachers value access to the learning resource portal.

The data above show that, despite teachers' extensive use of the Learning Resource Management System, they do not use it to its full potential. The study of Endozo et al. (2020) was parallel with the general results of the study in terms of the use of Learning Resource Management. Their study revealed that in terms of learning Resource Management System, teachers do not maximize the use of it.

Based on the study results, they encourage teachers to maximize the use of technology since they found significant results, and information was obtained for administrators, instructors, and students on how to improve usage of the system for teaching and learning.

Table 13 presents the tabulated data illustrating the teachers' ratings on the level of digital literacy in terms of online-based conference platforms, as claimed by the teachers, with a general mean of 3.93.

Due to the pandemic, teachers are now literate in the different online platforms used for conferencing. Teachers and school principals are especially interested in webinars and MS Teams for conferences at most meetings and focus group discussions.

Parallel to the study of Ramos and Soliven (2020), which revealed how teachers highly practice of online platforms for teachers. He even emphasized that experience, which showed a significant development, particularly in the use of video conferences. The findings revealed that webinar platforms helped respondents grow academically and personally. Furthermore, the researchers found that speakers' interactions with participants via visual and audiovisual presentations are valuable tools for teaching and learning.

Table 14 shows the survey responses regarding the level of pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in lesson planning. The data

show that teachers frequently incorporate ICT into lesson planning. That applies to all indicators of ICT Pedagogical Integration in lesson planning.

DO. 42, s. 2016 emphasizes that the daily lesson planning process can speed up using computers. Lesson plans can be written by hand or by computer. Schools use ICTs to store lesson plans prepared by their instructors. They can organize excellent lesson plans into a database or databank, post them on the school's website, or upload them to the LRMS portal. Subsequently, teachers can utilize the portal as a tool to prepare their daily lessons. By having a library of lesson plans at their disposal to use when getting ready for their daily classes, teachers can help one another in this way.

To conclude, the Level of Pedagogical Integration of Information and Communication Technology of the teachers in lesson planning is often integrated. Teachers are aware that creating lesson plans is affected by the use of technology. These findings form the basis for a more intensive exploration of the strategies employed by school heads in the delivery of technical assistance to teachers in creating lesson plans.

The study of König et al. (2021) is connected with the result of the study on the importance of ICT in creating lesson plans. As revealed by König et al. in their study, they highlight the use of ICT Pedagogical Integration in lesson plans as a situation-specific skill of teachers, being predicted by teacher knowledge and beliefs, and predicting observable teacher performance in class. Moreover, ICT Pedagogical Integration in lesson plans is affected by learning opportunities both in initial teacher education and in teacher professional development.

Table 15 reveals the data illustrating the level of pedagogical integration of information and communication technology regarding the preparation of instructional materials. Teachers frequently incorporate ICT into their instructional materials. Teachers demonstrate integration in the development of instructional materials by using digital tools. It may not seem surprising given that teachers have participated in numerous IM-related trainings and courses in undergraduate courses.

Overall, the data highlights the importance of technology and digital tools for teachers. These findings aid in understanding the significance of such integration in providing quality technical assistance and provide a basis for research and recommendations for future improvement of the teachers' skills.

Table 16 reveals that the teachers' pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in terms of the delivery of instruction is often 3.79.

Since the teachers are encouraged by the school heads to integrate ICT into the delivery of the lessons, it sheds light on the teachers' use of ICT in the delivery of instructions. The importance of instructional leadership, ongoing reinforcement, collaboration, monitoring, and evaluation in providing effective technical assistance when implementing ICT in the classroom.

In his study, Gragg R. (2021) emphasized the vital of use ICT in instruction delivery. His study revealed that using ICT in education contributes to the teaching and learning process by making learning more efficient or by giving it a previously unattainable dimension. ICT can encourage students to participate in collaborative learning and may be a significant motivating factor in their education. ICT is unquestionably the way for organizations to grow directly aligned with technology, and the field of education is no exception.

Table 17 presents the data illustrating the pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in terms of assessment of learning and finds that teachers often integrate with a 3.64 mean. Analyses of the data highlight teachers' agreement on essential topics, exemplifying the value placed on the importance of these in the assessment of learning. Teachers often use ICT in assessment because it provides prompt feedback, and information to guide education, teacher-made evaluation and differentiation based on the requirements of students.

The statement that the teacher used an automated QR code to evaluate the learner's performance (3.41) was notably the lowest integration level recorded. These findings may have affected on the frequent use of the teacher's strategy involving automated QR code the assessment.

The study by Kumar A. (2020), which mainly studied the effectiveness of ICT in the assessment of learning, revealed how teachers often use ICT as a tool in assessing learning. The study by Kumar likewise revealed the optimistic impact of integrating ICT in assessing learning. The optimistic view he mentioned in the conclusion of his study revealed that the teachers who successfully implement ICT will lead change, which is more about influencing and empowering teachers and supporting them in their engagement with students in learning. It may also help them with a better assessment of learning.

Table 18 shows between teachers' digital literacy on online conference platforms and pedagogical integration in lesson planning. However, the relationship is a weak negative correlation. It implies that even though there is a high level of literacy an online-based conference platform has nothing to do with or does not have a connection with ICT Pedagogical Integration in lesson planning.

Productivity Software Tools and Lesson Planning have a Weak Negative Correlation, it implies that even if teachers are highly literate in productivity software tools it has less Pedagogical Integration in Lesson Planning. Website Browsing to Lesson Planning was also found to be a weak positive correlation, it implies that even teachers can navigate and utilize Website browsing, it was only sometimes used in pedagogical integration of ICT.

Social Media and Learning Resource Management Systems to Pedagogical Integration in Lesson Planning were found Weak Positive Correlation, It means that teachers are highly literate in Social Media and Learning Resource Management Systems the frequent Pedagogical Integration of ICT in terms of Lesson Planning.

The results of the relationship between lesson planning and online-based conferences using platforms are similar to the results of the study by Edi et al. (2021), in which they studied lesson planning. They revealed in the study that using online-based conference platforms is significantly related to lesson planning based on their conclusion from their research that, to address the demands of designing learning programs in the modern age, online-based lesson plans can occur as a development.

Teachers can use multimedia devices remotely to have a balanced ratio of classroom and online-based face-to-face classes. With school funding, new learning resources, Teachers abilities to operate digital platforms, and student needs, online-based lesson plans will occur. The primary elements of online-based learning programs are the capability and ability of teachers to create a plan that would greatly benefit learning.

Table 19 shows that the level of digital literacy in terms of productivity software tools, website browsing, social media platforms, learning resource management, and online-based conference platforms has a weak relationship to the integration of ICT in the preparation of instructional materials.

Instructional materials are important tools for the growth and advancement of learning. The use of ICT in its preparation may not require extensive ICT literacy. However, based on the results, there is still a weak positive correlation that may somehow affect, although it may not directly impact, ICT in the preparation of instructional materials.

Based on the study of Aziz et al. (2019), some points of integration of ICT in teaching content, such as the preparation of instructional materials, will enable the teachers to offer a learner-centered learning environment, depending on the learners' interests and needs. The use of ICT for differentiating instruction allows teachers to provide more appropriate, authentic, and personalized learning activities that are most relevant to the learner's learning style. This may explain why using software tools, web browsing, learning resource management, and social media platforms has little correlation with the preparing of instructional materials.

Table 20 presents the correlation between digital literacy and the integration of ICT in teaching in terms of the delivery of instruction. This shows that a weak positive correlation has little impact, but it could not be enough to claim that it is correlated with the delivery of instruction.

However, It implies that teachers are digitally literate in Productivity Software Tools, Social Media, and Learning Resource Management System and frequently integrate ICT in the Delivery of Instructions.

On the other hand, there is a weak negative correlation between website browsing and online-based conference platforms and the delivery of instruction, It suggest that even teachers are highly literate, the Pedagogical Integration of ICT decreases. However, in the study of Kagyera et al. (2024), there is a strong interdependence linking ICT tools and lecturers' teaching practices, which portrays the essence of integrating ICT tools in

teaching. The implication is that adopting ICT for teacher education improves lecturers' teaching methodology and, eventually, their learners' attitudes towards teaching.

Table 21 presents the Level of Digital Literacy in terms Productivity Software Tools have significant relation to Pedagogical Integration in terms of Assessment of Learning but does have weak positive correlation. This may imply that teachers consistently use software tools for fast learning assessment. Teachers often use Excel and other tools to make assessing more efficient.

On the other hand, website browsing, social media platforms, learning resource management systems, and online-based conference platforms were all found to be not significantly correlated. This implies that they are not enough to claim that they have a significant relationship. It implies that even teachers are digitally literate the less frequency on pedagogical integration in ICT.

Majid (2020) presented the results of his study, and everybody agrees that assessment is an essential part of the teaching and learning process. ICT plays a significant part in simplifying the assessment process for educators. With the growing use of ICT, assessments are conducted in novel and creative ways. Is also how the recording and grading made it easy. Not only this, the students are being empowered to use online or web-based assessments, which helps the students.

Table 22 depicts the various challenges that teachers face when integrating information and communication technology into their instruction. According to teachers, the above statements were all encountered at least once, with a mean of 2.99.

Nonetheless, teachers faced obstacles in integrating ICT. Teachers must take advantage of available ICT resources because they may face the issues on occasion.

Teachers face a significant challenge in integrating information and communication technology (ICT) into their teaching. This barrier can manifest in various ways, each leading to a lack of pedagogical integration. By addressing these challenges, teachers, with the help of school heads, can develop the steps needed to effectively integrate ICT into teaching, resulting in increased student engagement.

Lack of teacher expertise or technical support for integrating ICT needs a multi-approach that includes funding for professional development, access to top-notch training programs, the supply of continuing resources and support, and the promotion of an innovative and collaborative culture within educational communities. Giving teachers the tools, resources, and encouragement, they require to incorporate ICT into the teaching task successfully.

Unavailability of genuine/licensed ICT Software tools hinders the integration into the teaching task. It will lead to performance issues, functionality limitations, and compatibility problems that hinder their ability to integrate technology into teaching effectively.

The unstable internet connectivity can challenge teachers when administering online assessments, quizzes, or exams. Technical glitches, network disruptions, or slow loading times may compromise the integrity and fairness of assessments, leading to inaccuracies in grading and assessment results. Moreover, delayed or inconsistent internet connectivity can hinder teachers' ability to provide timely feedback to students and affect their teaching tasks.

Absence of internet connection affects Interactive online activities, collaborative projects, and virtual discussions. However, unstable internet connectivity can hinder students' ability to participate in these activities, leading to disengagement, frustration, and reduced learning outcomes. Students may experience difficulties submitting assignments or participating in online discussions, which can negatively impact their academic performance and motivation.

Teachers frequently have a limited amount of time available for each lesson or instructional period, and they must cover a wide range of curriculum content and learning goals. As a result, integrating ICT into teaching may be perceived as an additional task that competes with other instructional priorities. Teachers may struggle to find sufficient time to plan, prepare, and implement ICT-enhanced lessons while ensuring that meet curriculum requirements.

When teachers lack confidence in using ICT, they may be hesitant to incorporate technology into their teaching tasks. It may lead to opportunities to improve lessons with multimedia content, interactive activities, and online resources. As a result, students may not benefit from the full range of learning experiences that ICT can provide.

Without adequate training, teachers may lack the knowledge to integrate ICT into their teaching task effectively. It can result in underutilization of technology in the classroom, with teachers sticking to traditional teaching methods instead of exploring the potential benefits of ICT for enhancing learning experiences.

When teachers are uninterested in using ICT, they may be less likely to investigate and integrate technology tools and resources into their teaching task. This can lead to reluctance to incorporate technology into lessons, resulting in missed opportunities to enhance learning experiences and engage students with interactive and multimedia-rich content.

Access to computer hardware is essential for effectively integrating technology into classroom teaching. Without access to computers, teachers may struggle with digital tools, software applications, and online resources to enhance teaching and learning experiences. It can result in a reliance on traditional teaching methods and missed opportunities to engage students through interactive and multimedia-rich content.

Table 23 revealed the teachers' coping mechanisms for integrating pedagogical information and communication technology into their teaching tasks. Teachers claimed that in terms of coping mechanisms they use to overcome such challenges.

However, teachers claimed that they use coping mechanisms sometimes. It may imply that those challenges were experienced sometimes as well. Teachers, despite experiencing different challenges continuously, overcome the challenges.

When integrating information and communication technologies (ICTs), it enhances the teaching experience and benefits the learners. However, many teachers face challenges due to a lack of knowledge in effectively integrating ICTs. Without the opportunity to attend the trainings and workshops, an individual is results in independent learning.

Teachers who struggle to incorporate information and communication technologies (ICT) into their lessons due to a lack of technical support turn to their peers, institutional leaders, and specialists for assistance in troubleshooting technical issues.

Addressing the lack of genuine or licensed ICT software tools is crucial for ensuring the optimal data performance that teachers need when integrating ICT. Pirated software may lack the reliability, stability, and performance of genuine or licensed versions. Teachers may encounter bugs, glitches, and compatibility issues that hinder productivity and disrupt workflows. To cope with this, institutional heads and teachers determine the specific ICT software tools that are essential for their teaching tasks and then purchase genuine or licensed ICT software tools to effectively maximize the benefits of the software.

Teachers who are having difficulty incorporating information and communication technologies (ICT) into their lessons due to a lack of technical support seek assistance in troubleshooting technical issues from their peers, institutional leaders, and specialists. To cope with this problem, seek technical support from internet providers and address connectivity issues that result in minimizing disruptions to teaching caused by unstable internet connections.

Without internet access, teachers are unable to access online resources such as educational websites, digital libraries, and multimedia content. It limits access to information, interactive learning materials, and supplementary resources that can enrich the learning experience. To cope with this problem, teachers seek administrative support for internet connectivity, which prioritizing reliable internet infrastructure and technology within the school.

Effective ICT Pedagogical Integration requires a mindful analysis of pedagogical strategies that use technology to improve instruction. A lack of time could result in unreliable technological integration. Rather than just using technology for its own sake, teachers take time to think about integrating it in ways that improve teaching and learning. To fill this gap, teachers seek allotted time for preparation for integrating ICT in classroom teaching; this leads to more effective pedagogical approaches, instructional strategies, and assessment procedures.

When utilizing ICT in the classroom, teachers could be afraid of making mistakes or running into technical difficulties, which could make them doubt their abilities. One of

the biggest challenges to trying out and innovating with technology-enhanced teaching methods is the fear of failure. To manage, teachers seek motivation from peers to use ICT in classroom teaching, which helps build confidence and the knowledge needed to integrate ICT into their teaching.

When teachers face a lack of training in using information and communication technologies (ICT) in classroom teaching, it can create barriers to effective technology integration. In order to cope, teachers seek professional development opportunities focused on ICT Pedagogical Integration. They request workshops, LAC sessions, or training from school administrators or seek external training resources themselves.

Some teachers may believe that their preferred teaching methods or pedagogical approaches are incompatible with ICT Pedagogical Integration. To cope with this problem, teachers seek goals in using ICT in the classroom where flexible and adaptable ICT tools are shown that can be incorporating into teaching styles and instructional strategies.

Without access to computer hardware, teachers may struggle to prepare digital materials, lesson plans, and instructional resources that incorporating technology. By implementing solutions such as requesting administration support for computer hardware, schools can help address the challenge of limited access to computer hardware for teachers, enabling them to maximize the use of technology more effectively in classroom teaching and enriching learning experiences for all students.

Conclusions

1. Even though teachers sometimes run into difficulties, they always use word processing software for their everyday teaching tasks in the classroom. They frequently use spreadsheet tools, which are more often used in the preparation of grades. Teachers are digitally literate at creating and presenting using presentation tools due to their regular use for their teaching task. Integrating different strategies and techniques in teaching involves browsing websites with high frequency.

It also concludes that the frequent use of social media for teaching-related tasks has a high literacy rate in its utilization. Teachers should have access to the learning resource portal. It shows how digitally literate teachers are by frequently accessing the learning resource portal. It also comes to the conclusion that teachers are now literate with the different video conferencing online platforms.

In most cases of meetings and even focus group discussions, teachers and school heads are particularly familiar with the use of webinars and MS Teams for conferences. Furthermore, it concludes that there is a high and very high literacy rate as a result of continued utilization and training provided by the school and ICT coordinators to ensure

teachers can cope with the digitalization needs of the twenty-first century. The use of digital literacy in teaching tasks can increase with frequent use.

2. Based on the analysis, the level of teachers' pedagogical integration of ICT was high. The level of pedagogical integration of information and communication technology in terms of lesson planning, preparation of instructional materials, delivery of instruction, and assessment of learning were all often used by the teachers.

3. Furthermore, it concludes that there is a significant relationship between digital literacy and information and communication technology in lesson planning, as teachers integrate ICT in the planning of lessons and frequently use it in the teaching task. This concludes that teachers are more likely to successfully integrate ICT tools and resources into their lesson plans if they have high levels of digital literacy.

Moreover, it concludes that online-based conferences and assessments of learning to productivity of software tools have also significant relationship. Online conferences provide dynamic platforms for teachers to gather and share knowledge, experiences, and insights through the use of productivity software tools. Assessment of learning enables teachers to assess students' proficiency and understanding using productivity software tools.

4. The problems met in information and communication technology in teaching claimed sometimes encountered. Teachers continued to face obstacles when integrating ICT. However, they make use of the available ICT resources. Digital literacy among teachers can lead to the successful integration of ICT into teaching and learning activities.

5. Furthermore, it concludes that the coping mechanisms of the teachers' integrating information and communication technology into their teaching tasks were sometimes integrated. While it helps teachers navigate challenges in integrating ICT into their teaching tasks, it is essential to recognize that individual circumstances may vary. Providing ongoing support, resources, and professional development opportunities tailored to teachers' needs can facilitate successful ICT Pedagogical Integration and enhance teaching effectiveness. Based on the outcomes, the training program might be suggested to enhance ICT Pedagogical Integration in the classroom.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn, the following are recommended:

1. Since most respondents are found to be digitally high and highly literate, teachers are recommended to continue innovation and updates on current trends in productivity software tools, website browsing, social media platforms, learning resource management systems, and online-based conference platforms, as technology is constantly evolving. This can be achieved through a training program focusing on the latest technological advancements and best practices. Ensuring teachers remain at the forefront of

educational technology and can effectively leverage these tools to enhance student learning outcomes.

2. According to the findings of the study, most respondents claimed they often integrate ICT. Teachers may continuously improve and enhance their skills through different trainings. Continuous support and capacity building for professional development for teachers are essential to attain Technologically Advanced Classroom Instruction. Additionally, commitment to continuous improvement and professional development will lead to more effective and engaging instruction, that better prepares students for the demands of the digital age.

3. Based on the results of the study, no significant relationship or weak correlation between Digital literacy and Pedagogical Integration, it was found that given the generally high level of teachers' digital literacy and often to sometimes frequent integration of ICT in the teaching task, it is suggested that teachers may intensify and continue the pedagogical integration of ICT to be able to help the school with the development and improvement of the learners. Systematic monitoring and evaluations are necessary to guarantee the quality of technical assistance. Training programs should be updated continuously to include the latest technological advancements and pedagogical strategies, ensuring that teachers are well-prepared to leverage new tools and methods.

4. In line with the results, problems met by the teachers that are sometimes encountered, school heads may also continue to provide technical assistance and supervision to teachers to improve their integration through different programs to help the teachers and learners. These programs can include ongoing professional development workshops that focus on the latest educational technologies and effective pedagogical strategies using ICT in the classroom. Additionally, schools can establish dedicated technology support teams to assist teachers with troubleshooting and implementing new tools. Creating a resource center with up-to-date materials and guides on ICT integration can also serve as a valuable asset for educators seeking to enhance their technical skills.

5. In connection to the results of the study, the coping mechanism of the teachers in integrating information and communication technology into their teaching tasks were all sometimes, School heads are recommended to provide effective instructional leadership support to Teachers. Strategic resource allocation, management of instructional programs, promotion of positive learning environments, development of leadership skills and knowledge, and provision of technical assistance can significantly affect professional growth and school success in integrating ICT.

6. In line with the findings of the study that ICT integration is often, it is suggested that educational practitioners, policymakers, and researchers understand the need to enrich instructional leadership and improve the delivery of technical assistance to help teachers cope with their challenges in integrating ICT. This enhancement involves providing school leaders with the necessary training and resources to guide and support their staff effectively. Instructional leaders should be well-versed in the latest educational

technologies and pedagogical strategies to mentor teachers in their ICT integration efforts.

7. Relevant to the findings of the study, it is suggested that Teachers may apply the training program to enhance the integration of ICT into their pedagogical practices. By leveraging the training, educators can develop more interactive and engaging teaching methods that utilize digital tools and resources effectively. This integration can lead to improved student outcomes, as technology can provide diverse and innovative ways to present information, facilitate collaboration, and assess learning. This continuous enhancement of pedagogical skills through ICT integration will not only enrich the learning experience but also prepare students for a digitally driven world.

8. Since digitalization and technology are continuously developing and emerging, the research may not seem applicable in the next ten years. However, it is recommended to design a parallel or comparative study to ascertain the degree of digital literacy among teachers in integrating ICT into the classroom and other relevant tasks. This future-oriented research should involve regular intervals of data collection to track changes and trends over time.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the researcher first secured consent from all participants, including school heads, master teachers, and teachers, prior to their participation. Respondents were given clear information about the research's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, and they were free to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained to protect participants' privacy, ensuring that their responses and personal information were secure and not disclosed without their express consent. Furthermore, the research was carried out with integrity, honesty, and transparency, without any form of deception or manipulation.

The researchers followed the ethical guidelines and standards established by relevant institutions and regulatory bodies, such as the university and DepEd, including seeking approval from ethics committees or review boards.

Finally, the study's findings was reported accurately and objectively, without bias or distortion and promote the welfare of the participants without causing harm, while also ensuring that the respondents are safe and secure throughout the study.

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